

BRAZIL AS A PRECURSOR OF THE 4TH AGRICULTURAL REVOLUTION

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7178547

Sergio Rodrigues de Souza

Agronomy student. Scientific Consultant. E-mail: SergioRodrigues52@hotmail.com.

Vinicius da Silva Santos

Biologist. Master in Education and Technologies from Vale do Cricaré College. Professor of the State Education Network of Espírito Santo. Email: viniiciusbiologo33@gmail.com.

Sandro Dau

Post-Doctor in Philosophy from the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro. Email: sandrodau2008@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

The present work addresses the issue of Brazil as a precursor of the 4th agricultural revolution. It is a matter of extreme need, since even being played as an exponent in the production of grains and animal protein, respecting all environmental protocols, much is said against Brazilian agribusiness and rural producers. This is a theoretical essay based on field studies and analysis of situations observed and described by technicians, extension workers, producers, scientists and researchers linked to the agricultural area. The general objective is to clarify the revolutionary dimension of Brazilian agricultural production and the pioneering spirit of individuals who work, directly and indirectly, in the field. Brazil has been showing itself, for more than half a century, as a major producer of agricultural products, commodities, technologies, innovation and development, making use of what is most elementary in its epistemic evolutionary achievement in the agricultural sector: the search for knowledge of objects about which it focuses, namely, nature, soil, plants, climate, animals and microorganisms and their respective behaviors in response to the management applied to them. This makes it an exporter, in addition to consumer goods, of pioneering technologies, which result in higher productions and with a greater positive impact on the environment and the consumer population.

Keywords: Brazilian agricultural production; Agribusiness; Agricultural Revolution; innovation in knowledge and technological development.

INTRODUCTION

Since the emergence of man on Earth, the relationship between man and nature has followed a pattern of conflicts, for the simple fact that the former has its own rules, based on the climate and this has made plants adapt their respective biological cycles determined by such conditions. In order to meet their intrinsic needs, humans began to select plants that could be consumed freely, as well as their fruits. consumed, texture, flavor and, most essential, if they could be grown in their private spaces, in their respective domestic backyards.

This unique condition of human beings, in which their hands and the bipedal condition allow them to manipulate different elements, combined with their intellect, which leads them to produce infinite questions about all the things that surround them, with a pragmatic determinism, where their Survival is the central point of all primitive man's struggle with nature and an alleged dominion over it.

In his egocentric struggle for the absolute domination of nature, he understood that without knowledge of its states and dynamisms, he would always end up where he started: in the void of his own ignorance about everything! But, one is faced with another problem, even more complex, where to seek knowledge about the changing seasons of nature, about plants, animals, the production cycles of each of them and their requirements, if it didn't even exist before everything ?

This challenge posed made the man of antiquity take the observation of phenomena, in an attempt to understand cultures and their behaviors, as an epistemological tool that would help him produce the much-desired knowledge he needed to overcome the challenges that were presented to him. . Each form of treatment provided in agricultural production should be meticulously analyzed to determine whether its practice suited that situation and how the crops responded. Thus, technology was born, the study of technique, the knowledge on how to offer treatment to plants and obtain the maximum production from them, as a response.

Over the millennia, man has proceeded in this way in relation to the challenges of nature, always trying to understand the elements that compose it and, with this, the acquired knowledge opens new possibilities of hypotheses until it is transformed into knowledge and theories, with the potential for be tested at the field level. With this, man discovers that he cannot overcome nature; it can become its eternal apprentice and, through this process, create new structures of knowledge and overcoming.

This is what has been happening with Brazil for many decades, in which, as it is located in a complex geothermal belt, ranging from the subtropical to the equatorial climate, with

extreme climatic, rainfall and pedological variations, it obliges producers, technicians, researchers and Brazilian scientists to unravel the mysteries that involve the entire tropic condition typical of the country, seeking adaptation of cultivars, plants, production, productivity, phenology.

Because Brazil is an exotic country, more specifically, in relation to its various biomes, every time it is faced with a challenging situation, the alternative is to find viable and plausible solutions through applied research and, once again, it is faced with with an instigating challenge: where to look for support and knowledge to support the investigation? Thus, the solution is to develop knowledge from the human action itself on the elements that are available to the farmer and technicians.

BRIEF CLARIFICATION ON THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURE IN THE HUMAN EXISTENTIAL CONDITION

Throughout human history, since human beings were able to perform feats that had the power to change their perspectives regarding the future of their existence and survival, the dominance and domestication of plants and animals represent a separate chapter in their history. Social. The understanding that plants needed light and aerated soils for the fullest development of their roots, with this, providing greater harvests can be one of the most relevant discoveries for agriculture in all its history and that occurred from observations and tests. . From then on, the need arises to develop a tool that could carry out the service of decompacting the soil on a large scale. From such empirical necessity, the man of antiquity invents the plow. The invention of the plow [*occurred around 4500 BC .*] is still considered as the greatest technological revolution in the entire history of agricultural mechanization (SILVEIRA, 2000), because it made possible the aeration of soils, which allows the roots of cultures to explore the fertile layer of the agricultural horizon, with greater power of action and less resistance to its development.

Cattle, which had been domesticated millennia before [*around 8500 BC .*], began to be used to pull plows , which represented another unprecedented advance in human history and which would provide them with a new leap of development, because in addition to being a powerful traction force, large areas intended for planting could be prepared in a shorter time (CARVALHO, BARBOSA and MCDOWELL, 2005), thus taking advantage of the window of opportunity for planting crops that have always been linked to the photoperiod and rainfall regime, that is, biological and climatic factors.

Another situation that marks the development of agriculture is the selection of plants, a process that is carried out according to the productive capacity of the chosen crops-varieties, resistance to pests and diseases, tolerance to water stress [*both due to lack and excess of water in the soil*], adaptation to other adverse climatic conditions to those of its origin, soil types and agricultural management.

For many millennia, these three revolutionary situations linked to agricultural development meant the elevation of the human *status quo to the status of a genius and everything seemed that it would persist, ad infinitum* , were it not for the perception that, with the exponential increase in population, a fact that Solon (638-558 BC) had already noticed and that during his government, as legislator of the Polis of Athens (Greece), he implemented ways to curb the population explosion, in order to guarantee the people's food, without the risk of hunger, especially due to the fact that all natural resources are limited, such as land, water, crop production capacity, pest and disease control and other inclement weather, some predictable, others not.

In 1798, economist Thomas Robert Malthus (1766-1834) wrote a powerful article in which he dealt with demographic expansion conflicting with food production in the world and even dared to make projections for some developing nations. His thesis was based on the principle that food production grew in arithmetical proportion (so defined 1:2:3:4:5...), while population grew in **geometric proportion** (so defined 1:2:4:8 :16:32...). As a result, agricultural production capacity would be able to meet consumption demands only up to the second generation and, from then on, no matter how much it was improved, it would fall short of needs and even if it expanded its production potential five times, in fifth generation could only serve one third of the population (MALTHUS, 1996).

The idea and its systematic analysis are brilliant; however, Malthus is speaking of a Nordic country, with limitations of all kinds and of all elements, including an element that tropical countries possess on a large scale and over which man has very little [*or no*] control, which is the photoperiod, two distinct periods throughout the year, which are related to intense rainfall [*rainy period*] and a period of low [*or very low*] rainfall, so essential for many cultures to maintain their phytobiological processes active and regular. Adapting crops to such conditions of light and darkness represents, even today, an intense challenge for geneticists working with plant breeding, and for farmers, an incredible battle to adjust the planting windows of commercial plant varieties, balancing light hours. -darkness with rainfall and water demand curve.

At the time when he carried out his analytical studies on the relationship between population growth *and* agricultural production, the available techniques and technologies were far from what was necessary to face a problem of such magnitude. Every scientist, however great he may be [*or proves himself to be*], has his analyses, interpretations, deductions and conclusions defined and determined by the historical moment in which he is inserted, together with all the technological apparatus that is available to help technicians. In facing the challenges and problems posed by society, T. Malthus was not wrong in his studies and inferences, and his analysis, even limited by the production conditions of the 18th century, the meager technical and scientific knowledge about the biology of plants and all their potential and the precarious living conditions of the city of London, a legacy he left was to think of ways to overcome the challenges of producing more food, exploring the potential of plants and soils to respond to such demands. The result is what is constantly witnessed in countries such as Brazil showing a capacity to surpass their production each year, also adding management and production techniques increasingly linked to conditions of environmental sustainability. .

Along with these technical innovations, it has been sought, through the knowledge of meteorology, the most propitious moments to carry out the sowing of the different agricultural crops, each one with its specific photoperiod and unique water needs. It cannot be said that there are already available technologies capable of determining the ideal point for sowing crops, and due care is taken when stating such a thing, because the studies already carried out and proven present an optimal [*ideal*] window for carrying out the agricultural management in commercial crops; however, the climate and its variations is something that is completely out of the absolute control of man and the changes that have occurred and their influences directly affect the occurrence of infestation of pests and diseases, interfering with the final results of the productions.

It is at this point that rural extension and agricultural research are necessary for the full development of agricultural enterprises, because through tests and technical records, there are greater possibilities of having approximate notions of the phenomena that affect the cultures, being able to anticipate infestations that could lead to the total destruction of crops. Thus, theoretical knowledge is not enough, it is necessary to add to this empirical knowledge that, once allied to what is known as recommended by the academy, a consistent understanding is formed about the occurrences in the field, the behavior of plants and insects, mites, protozoa, fungi, etc.

Unfortunately, human beings have always been concerned with what they can see and, in agriculture, what can be seen is usually a symptom, never being able to be seen as a cause

and, it is there, at this inflection point that lies what can be determined as the most emblematic [*and necessary*] of all agricultural revolutions because humanity was crossed and that, in the same way, it has provoked.

In this scenario, Brazil shows itself as a producer of revolutionary agricultural technologies, unmatched in history, not because it is the greatest power in the production of grains and *commodities* today, but because of its constant search to reduce the financial costs of its enterprise. and in this, he ended up discovering that the capacity to increase the production of the cultivars-varieties that he uses has very narrow limits, considering their genetic potential; however, through genetic improvement, the potential of responses to management proved to be very high until this detail found its bottleneck [*its bottleneck*] and, once again, Brazilian producers showed themselves to be pioneers in seeking, creating , develop and implement agricultural practices that can be considered as the agricultural *revolution* that will completely change the history of agriculture: soil management, no longer with an exclusive view to the plant and cultivated cultivars, but aiming at the enrichment of the entire pedological flora and the nutrition of microbiological cultures that are responsible for transforming minerals [*organic and chemical*] into nutritive sources for plants, enabling their full vegetative development [*photosynthesis and protein-energy synthesis*], transforming all this into mineral elements available for consumption human and animal.

Brazilian scientific research has been improving techniques and managements that can lead to the *optimal use* of fertilizers and fertilizers applied, so that, in addition to avoiding losses through volatilization, contamination of soils, groundwater, water and air, it reverts in results of increasingly higher agricultural productions, with a potentiating mass flow of crops superimposed on the main summer harvests. All of this becomes applied technologies, available to anyone willing to learn and use them.

It is important here to clarify what is understood as technology. Dorieldo dos Prazeres (2008) is the one who best presents a concept: he argues that,

Man works to obtain from nature the goods necessary to satisfy his needs. Human evolution is a process that until now has been characterized by the increasing domination of nature by man. Every time man tries to extract what he wants from nature, he feels that she is not there to serve him, he feels her hostility... know it, and only then master it. Each time this happens, knowledge expands, and then consciousness develops... Thus, technology is born. And what best represents, in our days, the predominance of man over nature is human knowledge added to the proper use of technology! (PRAZERES, 2008, sp).

André Marcel Voisin (1903-1964) was one of the first agricultural scientists to state that the weight of what lives below the earth is greater than the weight of those who live above it, in a clear reference to the importance of the metabolic actions of minerals [*organic and inorganic substances*], carried out by microorganisms [*fungi and bacteria*] that inhabit the sub-surface layer of the Earth and that contribute greatly to the transformation of nutrients into absorbable forms for commercially exploited plants and their consumers.

Completely out of sight, there is an effusive action of mineral decomposition, carbon sequestration, burning of organic matter, cation exchanges, neutralization of chemical elements harmful to plants, which require the mobilization of various nutrients and organic compounds. All this requires a range of knowledge that cannot be acquired satisfactorily, because it is not available to everyone; it can only be acquired, if not, through the daily monitoring of the use of developed technologies applied to crops and soil management.

Brazil has been standing out in several segments of commercial agriculture, with the use of genetically improved seeds [*either through conventional breeding or through Biotechnology - Genetically Modified Organisms (GMO)*], with high rates of positive responses and this is due to its investment in sustainable agricultural practices, all of which are based on the principle that the soil is the agent that should receive the maximum amount of direct and indirect investments. The plants reveal the state of the soil system [*fauna and flora*] and, from the interpretation of the symptoms, answers to the challenges posed are sought and the result is more innovation, more technology reverted to production systems and, as a consequence, new agricultural production records, with an increasingly sustainable agricultural system. What was called the *4th Agricultural Revolution* is, for Brazilian producers, the expansion of their knowledge on how to make the soil and its macro and microbiological population more active in favor of the implemented culture.

WHAT WOULD BE THE 4TH AGRICULTURAL REVOLUTION?

Forbes Agro Magazine published, on June 2, 2022, an article entitled *Nobel in physics calls for a Fourth Agricultural Revolution*. This individual, laureate of the Nobel Prize in 1997 for his discovery in the field of Physics is Steven Chu, physicist at Stanford University and professor of molecular and cellular physiology and board member of Oatly, an oat food company. He talks [*as he can*] about what he considers the 3 (three) agricultural revolutions of history and calls for a 4th ^{one}, which would result in a human response to an inadequate and unproductive management regarding the use of natural resources and food production. .

An innovation in agricultural production systems to the point of being categorized, by history, as a global revolution would depend on having an entire system decomposed by archaic techniques and that its use was causing such severe damage to the environment that it required a radical change, without this affecting production mechanisms and current demands for food. This is not what is shown in the current scenario, in which every day, new research is carried out, in an attempt to find ways to increase the productivity of the exploited crops and the efficiency of the inputs used, which in response has been the reduction of direct and indirect losses, resulting in less aggression to the environment and, each time this happens, knowledge and knowledge increase exponentially, opening new perspectives for scientific investigation.

Steven Chu talks about what he advocates as essential for sustainable agriculture and what he understands as a new revolution in the agricultural production system. According to him,

We need better crops with less fossil-based fertilizers and pesticides. There is an opportunity to restore the carbon in the soil that we have been depleting since the beginning of agriculture. There is a need for plants that are more resistant to heat and drought. There is a need to rethink beef and dairy production, [*since*] if beef and dairy were a country, its roughly five gigatons of CO₂ equivalent a year would be more emissions than any other country, and in fact, they are equal to the [*emissions*] of the US (emissions) at the moment. And, if land rest areas, between one crop and another, are used to grow biomass for carbon capture, these plants must be optimized for growth through genetic engineering (CHU, 2022, sp). [Italics ours].

All topics listed by Chu (2022) are relevant and necessary to be analyzed with due care about their impacts [*direct and indirect*] on the present and future of nations, especially those whose economic survival is based on agricultural production. . However, revolutions happen from innovations, studies, systematic analyses, deep and broad interpretations of the systems and mechanisms still used in the present, which produces a more accurate understanding of things, allowing enlightening syntheses and, most importantly, , field research, produced from empirical observations, tests, field trials, comparisons and refutations, until the scientific truth is found, which can be deduced as the cause of the [*positive and/or negative*] effects of actions and interactions humans with the environment.

Chu (2022) cites a set of norms and rules, without making the slightest reference on how to achieve such results, in the short, medium and long term. The initial idea and its first placement is the dream of consumption of every producer, to produce more and better using less fertilizers and chemical fertilizers, especially due to the high cost, caused, in particular, by the cost of transport. Agricultural pesticides, for the most part, protected by patents from multinational companies, have an increasing impact on the cost spreadsheet and it seems, at

first glance, as an inefficiency in their pest and disease control action, whether due to resistance from the latter. to molecules or due to inappropriate use holds a more complex and deeper explanation in which, with the increasing increase in the potential production capacity of plants, in the process of genetic development, it is one thing in favor of the other; that is, the increase in the potential capacity of grain and protein production, assimilation and carbon chain formation, gas exchange with the external environment, among other things, occurs to the detriment of the potential for resistance to the natural enemies of each species.

As for the mechanisms of carbon fixation (C), this is linked to the amount of nitrogen (N) that can be offered in the form of organic matter, and it is not just a matter of leaving the residue of agricultural crops available; it is necessary to work towards ensuring that it is and presents itself in such a way in size, volume and uniform distribution on the ground so that the entire area is benefited. Use agronomic techniques that allow lower losses of Nitrogen (N) to the atmospheric air, applying appropriate doses to the requirements of each crop, in particular. With regard to resistance to drought and heat, this condition is a euphemism, because being every vegetable composed of 90% to 95% of Hydrogen (H), Oxygen (O) and Carbon (C); the most that can be believed is in the development of plants with *tolerance* [*greater than the existing ones*] to such stress conditions [*caloric and hydric*] and that can obtain higher production responses than those that are exploited, within agronomic precepts, with economic interests.

When reference is made to raising beef and dairy cattle, the glimpse is the European and North American mega farms, in which they are closed systems, with real difficulties in applying solid and liquid waste in pasture and forage production areas. and forage for the production of food for the herd, which in fact will produce high concentrations of ammonia (NH₃). Mega confinements end up producing thousands of tons of waste within a relatively short period, which becomes a nuisance. When there are possibilities of application to forage crops, this changes, because the mineral nutrients present in cattle manure are highly absorbable by forage crops in development, which require high quality organic matter, in addition to nitrogen and carbon and, for this reason, sequester large amounts of masses of atmospheric carbon, in order to carry out its vegetative-biological cycle.

In this, what we have as a problem is the [*legal and technical*] condition for discarding this material, a by-product of food and animal production, so necessary for the nutrition of the microorganisms that live working in the soil, taking care of the maintenance of its biofertility, promoting the transformation of nutrients into metabolizable energy available to plants, which, in turn, will promote food production for both humans and animals.

Regarding the fallow of agricultural areas, this is a very old theme, in which the Brazilian aborigines already used so that the areas used could recover, in terms of their fertility and even in relation to the population of microorganisms, coleopterans, annelids, small birds and other animals and plants. The discussion is complex when the producer sees his idle land as an expense and not as an investment, calculating the rest time from the point of view of what he does not gain in financial terms and not treating the situation, in itself, as a management that applies to its patrimony aiming at greater future investments in terms of recovering its potential, culminating in more dynamic production.

Everything that Chu (2022) puts as what he advocates a new evolution of the agricultural production system involves a subtle detail that, over the years, has been surreptitiously hijacked in Brazil, which is the integrated technical assistance to rural producers. Instead of a trained and prepared technical professional, within didactic precepts, with the mission of guiding the rural producer on how to explore his land, produce in quantity and quality, in harmony with the Environment, they left him without any support [*or left to their own knowledge*] and created the environmental inspection bodies, with their draconian rules for which, if not adopted, according to their cabinet view, the sanction is a fine and imprisonment.

The long-awaited new agricultural revolution should take place via education, transforming the relationship between human beings and the environment in which they live, without having to demonize them and, consequently, expel them from their lands. Rural producers need technical knowledge, evaluated and tested by research agents, such as universities and institutes [*public and private*], so that what is at the forefront of agronomic and zootechnical knowledge reaches them.

Regarding all the points listed by Chu (2022), Brazil has been a pioneer since the 1970s, in which it has stood out in the creation of machines and implements, genetic selection of plants and animals, rational use of natural resources and management of the environment. soil, with an increase in its agricultural production year after year, in addition to the detail that crop productivity has also increased as a result of investments in research on genetic improvement, botany and, notably, management [*of crops and, especially, of soil*].

BRAZIL AS A PRECURSOR OF THE 4TH AGRICULTURAL REVOLUTION

It is not as if each nation decides, autonomously, to become agricultural or industrial, exploiter of rare goods. Without knowing it, several analytical and comparative studies were carried out in England, to think about the best strategies for countries to act in relation to their

economic actions, and Karl Marx (1818-1883) reveals one of these studies that, “ According to Schwege's calculations, in 1823, the total extraction of diamond mines explored in Brazil did not reach, calculated, taking a period of eighty years, the price presented by the average production of sugar and coffee plantations during a year and a half ” (MARX, 1962, p. 8).²⁹

What is clarified with this epigraph is that, once the bias of the highest economic return has been determined, considering the inversion time, the alternative falls on the one with the best answer, having calculated all the details. In this case, the path to Brazil that showed itself, from the beginning, as the most promising, was to be an agricultural nation and this became reality with the creation of the Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation (EMBRAPA), which for more for 50 years has been working on the production of knowledge and technologies.

Much is said about Brazilian agricultural production and its production potential. Starting with Pero Vaz de Caminha (1450-1500) who, as soon as he arrived in Brazilian lands, took care to write a letter to Your Majesty reporting that the land was good and everything that was planted in it grew, without even having planted a grain of any culture. The most interesting thing is that Brazil [*the land that gave everything that was planted in it*] only had its agricultural embryo fomented after the arrival of the Portuguese Royal Family, in 1808, who came here fleeing the French conqueror Leon Bonaparte. As there was no production of vegetables, greens and vegetables, they imported a Dutch agronomist who began to produce such products in Tupiniquin lands.

Likewise, the Uruguayan writer Eduardo Galeano talks about the sugar produced in Brazil and how this commercial activity turned Brazilian soils, previously rich, into infertile structures. He reports that, “sugar devastated the Northeast. The humid strip of the coast, well watered by rain, had a soil of great fertility, very rich in humus and mineral salts, covered by tropical forests from Bahia to Ceará” (GALEANO, 1991, p. 72).

It continues to ramble, in a romantic and hallucinatory way, that, naturally born to produce food, the Brazilian northeast became a region of hunger. Where everything germinated with exuberant vigor, the sugar latifundia, destructive and overwhelming, left barren rocks, washed soils, eroded lands. At first, plantations of oranges and mangoes were established, which little by little,

²⁹The original: “According to the calculations of Eschwege, in 1823 the extraction in total of the diamond mines in Brazil in the alcanzaba, calculated on the basis of a period of eighty years, the price represented by the average product of the Brazilian plantations of sugar and coffee during año and medio” (MARX, 1962, p. 8).

They were abandoned and were reduced to small gardens that surrounded the plantation owner's house, exclusively reserved for the white planter's family. The fires that opened land to new sugarcane plantations devastated the forest and with it the fauna; Deer, wild boar, moles, rabbits, pacas and armadillos disappeared. The plant mat, flora and fauna were sacrificed, on the altars of monoculture, to sugar cane. Extensive production quickly depleted the soils. The rainforest became savannah (Op. Cit.).

Gilberto Freyre (1900-1987), who is from the Northeast, reports that, in Brazil, there were not only fertile lands, but patches of very fertile soils, but that, in general, Brazilian soils were poor, in terms of fertility (FREYRE, 2005). . It is very evident that the application of erroneous management techniques such as the abusive use of fires led the soils [*no longer so fertile*] to complete decay. It is said in Europe that the fertility of the soil is a reflection of its owner. Soil fertility is not an immutable and constant factor. It is always being lost, to a greater or lesser degree, varying with the region, the purpose for which the exploration is intended suffered and the varieties of crops applied, with need for nutrient replacement through appropriate agronomic practices (ABREU, 2018).

In this sense, Brazil has shown itself to be efficient in the studies, tests and application of techniques for the conservation of soil fertility, using mulch as a soil protective agent against the direct action of rain and against direct solar radiation. No-till planting in straw has been applied since the 1970s and the system adopted in Brazilian agriculture is the most efficient in the world, because the soil layers are not completely turned over after the implementation of the system on the properties, there are places where there are more than 50 (fifty) years without plowing for planting.

All of this implies extensive and in-depth studies on soil fertility, management techniques, mechanization and harvest results. Straw choppers adapted to grain harvesters were developed, so that there is greater uniformity in the distribution of straw throughout the area. And, with this technique, there was a reduction in the volume of herbicides used in crops to control weeds, which, as a consequence, keeps alive a variety of insects that perform biological control in crops, without any human intervention in the process.

Rural producers have invested in crop rotation, winter crops, in order to form layers of organic matter on the soil and thereby provide nitrogen and carbon fixation that will be used by commercial crops. Encompassing the arduous task of producing and recycling nutrients in the soil, crop rotation is effective as long as there is scientific knowledge about soil fauna and flora, fertility, rainfall and availability of human and technical-scientific resources (machines, inputs, etc.)).

It is already proven, through numerous research results and field trials, the damage caused by the practice of successive monoculture and thus, avoid its practice, as a mechanism of sustainable use of natural resources of the soil. In addition to rotating commercial crops, they implement a mix of cover, using winter crops, with the sole purpose of producing straw, which will become mulch, so essential for soil fauna and flora.

Capra argues that,

The practice of monoculture, in addition to carrying the strong risk that a large planted area will be destroyed by a single pest, also seriously affects the health of farmers and people living in agricultural [*exploited*] regions. The ecological imbalance caused by monocultures and the excessive use of chemical products has also resulted in a huge increase in the number of pests and diseases of plantations, fought by farmers by [*use*] spraying ever-increasing doses of pesticides, in a vicious circle of depletion and undoing. The damage to human health increased correlatively, as an increasing amount of toxic insecticides penetrated the soil, contaminated the water table and reached our table (CAPRA, 2002, p. 184).

Monoculture is harmful to the soil ecosystem because it moves a single group of nutrients, requires the same type of management, mobilizes nutrients it needs and leaves the rest in quantities that can harm other occurrences of maintenance of biochemical processes in soils. As a specific group of pesticides is used for entomological control, they end up causing the disappearance of certain groups of insects and microorganisms and also contribute to the emergence of resistant pests, creating the so-called aliens, a special group that no type of pesticide can control them.

Monoculture agriculture is one of the human activities that most interfere and change natural ecosystems. In these activities the soil can be compacted, degraded, contaminated or even carried away, reflecting the absence of organisms. On the contrary, in forested areas the soil is protected by the treetops and becomes less exposed to sunlight, preventing a significant loss of moisture to the atmosphere. In agricultural areas with monoculture plantations and conventional practices such as mechanization, uncovered soil and the use of fire, there is greater loss of moisture, in addition to less water infiltration and increase in soil temperature, making it more difficult to establish a vegetation cover. The change in land use for monoculture production affects physical and microbiological attributes and most chemical attributes of soils. What can be clearly seen is that the practice of monoculture also contributes to the reduction of local biodiversity (PERIN et al., 2021).

The need for crop rotation is also due to the fact that, in soil chemistry, there is *mass flow* and *diffusion* ; in which, the *mass flow* is the remainder of the fertilization that was made in the previous culture and was not totally absorbed by this one, but that is available to a culture

that has a requirement of such nutrients that are planted soon after. While *diffusion* is the attachment of these nutrients to the soil mass that are transformed into chelates, that is, a type of molecular structuring of chemical elements that are precipitated in the soil, unable to be assimilated by other cultures, in the short and medium term (ABREU , 2018). The more a single type of commercial crop is used, the more this chemical detail is accentuated, resulting in considerable economic losses and agronomic potential losses.

With regard to pesticides, with the creation of reverse logistics in relation to containers, more and more bottles are being collected each year, in which a safe destination is given to them, without the risk of them continuing to contaminate rivers, lakes, springs and people who make use of these vessels for domestic use.

In 1992, during *Eco92* , the United Nations (UN) already recommended the Integrated Management of Pests and Diseases, which advocated reductions in the application of pesticides in crops and commercial crops. Brazilian technicians and producers were already using techniques aimed at this objective, determining, through field studies, determinations of what would be biological populations and economic populations of insects and from the results achieved, using statistical calculations, guide for the use [*or no*] of specific pesticides, for each case, in order to control the weed population, avoiding economic damages to the agronomically exploited crop.

It is noteworthy that the Instituto Capixaba de Pesquisa Agropecuária [*former EMCAPA and currently INCAPER – INSTITUTO CAPIXABA DE PESQUISA E EXTENSION RURAL*], a research agency in the State of Espírito Santo, was a pioneer [*at a global level*] in research on the biological control of the borer. do-café (*Hypothenemus hampei*), started in the early 1980s, on the experimental farm located in the municipality of Linhares, in the interior of Espírito Santo. The differentiated management, with the use of shading, in the Conilon coffee plantations (*Coffea canephora*), using intercropping with rubber trees (*Hevea brasiliensis L* .) provided visibility to the Brazilian product, adding a unique value to it.

The final document of the meeting, entitled *Agenda 21* , guides that

Integrated pest management, which combines biological control, host plant resistance and appropriate agricultural practices, and minimizes the use of pesticides, is the best option for the future, as it ensures yields, reduces costs, is environmentally benign and contributes for the sustainability of agriculture. Integrated pest management must be closely associated with proper pesticide management to allow for the regulation and control of pesticides, including their trade, and the safe handling and disposal of pesticides, especially toxic and persistent pesticides (UN - AGENDA 21, 1995, p. 195 - Chapter 14).

The adoption of the *Precision Agriculture practice*³⁰ was another technological advance of Brazilian producers, in which fertilizers, fertilizers and pesticides are applied at variable rates, without harming the chemical composition of the soil, minimizing potential and actual damage to the Environment. Burning is not used in the sugarcane fields for harvesting, which allowed the life of sugarcane crops to almost double. The straw residues in the fields, bagasse and by-products are destined for energy production, animal nutrition or for burning in the boilers of the alcohol and sugar mills.

With the increase in planted areas and the progressive increase in productivity, Brazil began to consume more fertilizers than the amount produced domestically. The research answer : the creation of a technology to fix nitrogen from the air in the roots of plants through bacteria. Biological Nitrogen Fixation (BNF), currently present in 75% of the soybean cultivated area, is responsible for a direct savings of R\$ 2 billion per year in the purchase of nitrogen fertilizers. FBN also contributes to reducing energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions (BRASIL – EMBRAPA, 2018).

Brazilian cattle are almost entirely raised in pasture systems, in which their waste and other forms of gases are insufficient to meet the biological needs of forage crops, that is, the Brazilian animal production system is carried out in the most perfect harmonious condition with nature. The pastures are mostly shaded, offering adequate thermal comfort to the animals in the field. With the issue of shading of areas destined for pasture, this generates thermal comfort to the herds, taking care of a precept of respect for animal bioclimatology.

With few investments, the entire herd of Brazilian *vacuum cattle* can be accommodated in half of the area that is currently used for meat production, without requiring large investments.³¹ Every year Brazilian technicians, scientists and rural producers invest in technologies that are elaborated and developed from the knowledge acquired about the behavior of animals and plants, in a dialectical relationship of reciprocity and simultaneity between agricultural theory and practice.

Increasingly, properties have sought to control pests and diseases in their crops and herds through biological control; however, this represents a very complex issue, because as

³⁰“Precision Agriculture (PA) comprises a set of techniques and methodologies aimed at optimizing crop management and the use of agricultural inputs, providing maximum economic efficiency. PA tools allow the rational use of fertilizers and pesticides, ensuring the reduction of environmental impacts resulting from agricultural activity” (BRASIL, 2009, p. 4).

³¹On this topic, see the article by: SANTOS, Vinícius da Silva; SOUZA, Sérgio Rodrigues de. Potential use of degraded pasture areas for grain production as a strategy to reduce deforestation. In: Silveira, Jader Luís da. (Org.). *Agronomy and Livestock : Transformation and National Production - Volume 1*. Formiga (MG): Editora Real Knowing, 2022, pp. 83-96. [EBook].

crops and animals are genetically improved in order to become more productive, they end up losing in natural conditions of resistance and defense against parasites, insects and mites, fungi, nematodes. , etc., which inevitably leads to the use of chemicals for control.

Brazilian agricultural properties maintain, by law, 20% of their total area destined for permanent environmental preservation, along with protection of the banks of ponds, lakes, streams, rivers, hilltops, swamps. This makes the rural producer the greatest ally in the preservation of the ecosystem, since a much higher percentage is kept intact.

Every year, Brazilian producers come in partnership with technicians, researchers and scientists, trying to find and develop increasingly cleaner production alternatives, using organic procedures and, with this, less use of chemical and defensive fertilizers, in attempt to preserve the pedological fauna and flora. With this, cutting-edge technologies have been created, knowledge in the most diverse areas of biological, agronomic, veterinary and zootechnical knowledge.

Brazilian agricultural production has increased every year, reaching historical production records, and such gains are not due to the increase in planted area nor because of the abusive use of fertilizers. The cause is the application of decades of accumulated knowledge that has been applied in a reputable way. Due to the continental dimension of the country, in which almost all types of climate are found, investments in knowledge about the behavior of soils, animals and plants that adapt to each specific region, endowed with its particularities and singularities, were required from rural entrepreneurs and technicians, in partnership with companies for the genetic improvement of plants and animals, machinery and implements production industries, a symbolic exchange of information, knowledge and knowledge on such a scale that made Brazil, no longer *the country of the future* (ZWEIG, 1941).); but the *future* itself.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

When the subject is related to agricultural production, Brazil reveals itself as a self-taught in the subject and, everything it has achieved over decades of investment in research and application of results is due to a joint and coordinated effort between the Private Initiative and the Government. Public, through the efforts of producers, technicians, researchers, scientists, teachers and extension workers.

As some intend to misrepresent the image of an agricultural nation earned by the country, calling it a *farm*, where it acts as a producer and exporter of raw materials and importer

of industrialized goods, that is, it sells products without added value and buys, on the other hand, with added value and the weight of gold, the fact is quite another, because along with what is acquired from Brazil (*commodities* , meat, etc.), it takes with it production of unparalleled result of years of investment, in order to acquire knowledge, learned from direct contact with nature, observing and directly participating in the results.

Thanks to all the country's efforts in the evolution of its agricultural development process, much more *knowledge is exported* than products themselves. North American producers feel proud when they talk about the products and techniques created by Brazilian rural producers and that revolutionize the forms of production around the world, citing as an example the knife roller, an agricultural equipment that allows the shredding of straw and cover. dead, facilitating the handling and planting of the different cultures, allowing to avoid the use of fire and plowing, as an anticipation of the planting of the cultures.

Anyone who dares to say that the world needs a 4th agricultural revolution demonstrates total ignorance about the Brazilian system of agricultural production. Everything that has been achieved so far, in terms of technical-technological and scientific knowledge, is far short of the potential that producers and technicians, extension workers, researchers and scientists have yet to discover and, we affirm, because the knowledge of Brazilians about agriculture and livestock comes from their agronomic praxis, that is, from the direct result of their daily actions in nature and in harmony with it, listening to it, observing its responses to interferences and techniques applied in order to overcome the epistemological knowledge itself about the binomial agriculture. -nature.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC REFERENCES

ABREU, José Antonio Soares de. *Environmental education as a [possible] path to the development of a sustainable organic society* . São Paulo: PerSe, 2018.

BRAZIL. EMBRAPA *Vision 2030* : the future of Brazilian agriculture. Brasília (DF): Embrapa, 2018.

BRAZIL. Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Supply. Secretariat of Agricultural Development and Cooperatives. *Precision Agriculture* . Brasilia: Mapa/ACS, 2009.

CAPRA, Fritjof. *The hidden connections: Science for sustainable living*. São Paulo: Editora Cultrix, 2002.

CARVALHO, Fernando Antônio Nunes; BARBOSA, Fabiano Alvim; MCDOWELL, Lee Russell. *Feeding cattle on pasture*. Belo Horizonte: Editora Própria, 2005.

GALEANO, E. *The open veins of Latin America*. Rio de Janeiro: Editora Paz e Terra, 1991.
FREYRE, Gilberto. *Casa Grande & Senzala* . 50. Ed. Rio de Janeiro: Global, 2005.

MALTHUS, Thomas Robert. *Test on the population* . São Paulo: Nova Cultural, 1996. [Essay originally written in 1798].

MARX, Karl. *El Capital* . [Volume I]. La Habana: National Editorial of Cuba, 1962.
MCMAHON, Jeff. *Nobel Prize in Physics Calls for a Fourth Agricultural Revolution* . Available at: <https://forbes.com.br/forbesagro/2022/07/nobel-defisica-pede-uma-quarta-revolucao-agricola/?amp>. Accessed on 07/24/2022.

UN. *United Nations Conference on Environment and Development – Agenda 21* (1992). Brasília: Digital Library of the Chamber of Deputies, 1995.

PERIN, Liamara; VIEIRA, Elaine Santos; ANDRADE, Veronica dos Santos; SANTOS, Taiane Conceição dos; ARAÚJO-PIOVEZAN, Talita Guimarães; MENEZES, Breno Freitas; MENEZES, Vanessa Marisa Miranda; DANTAS, Jose Oliveira. Effects of monoculture and vinasse application on chemical, physical and biological soil attributes in a sugarcane growing area in Sergipe, Brazil. In: SOUSA, Carla da Silva; Lima, Francisco de Sousa; SABIONI, Sayonara Cotrim (Orgs.). *Agroecology : methods and techniques for sustainable agriculture - Volume 3*. São Paulo: Editora Científica, 2021, pp. 137-162. [EBook]

PRAZERES, Doriêdo Luiz dos. *Personal communication* , 2008.

SILVEIRA, Gastão Moraes da. *Machines for Planting and Driving Crops - Volume 2*. Viçosa: Learn Easy Editora, 2000.

ZWEIG, Stefan. *Brazil, a country of the future*. Rio de Janeiro: Guanabara, 1941